

LAVA DISCHARGE RATES DETERMINED FROM TANDEM-X IMAGERY FROM KĪLAUEA VOLCANO, HAWAII

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ABSTRACT

The ability to measure the discharge rate of lava during a volcanic eruption is of fundamental importance to tracking eruptive activity and associated hazards. While there are many means of measuring the volume rate of extruded lava, differencing of digital elevation models (DEMs) has provided exceptional results at volcanoes around the world. Topographic data derived from TanDEM-X synthetic aperture radar imagery span lava emplacement at Kīlauea Volcano, Hawai‘i, in 2011–2013. Differences between sequential TanDEM-X-derived DEMs reveal the four-dimensional evolution of Kīlauea’s lava flow field, which increased in thickness by up to 30 meters during that span. The volume and area of the lava flow field at each time step can be used to determine the average discharge rate of lava. During 2012, when all lava was erupted on land, the discharge rate was about half the volcano’s long-term average. No other measure of lava effusion was available at Kīlauea in 2012, demonstrating the importance of TanDEM-X DEM differences for volcano monitoring and hazards assessment.

Index Terms— Volcanoes, Synthetic Aperture Radar, Interferometry, Surface Topography, Hazards

1. INTRODUCTION

Numerous methods have been used to quantify lava effusion rates at volcanoes around the world (see [1] for a detailed review). In Hawai‘i, application of these methods is governed by specific eruptive circumstances, environmental conditions, and other constraints—for example, the existence of observable lava tubes, measurable gas emissions, cloud-free aerial or satellite imagery, or sufficient spatio-temporal resolution. Satellite-derived radar interferograms can be used to construct digital elevation models (DEMs) that show elevation change over time, which can be differenced to provide a measure of time-averaged discharge rate for subaerial lava flows. Such data can have excellent spatial and temporal resolution and are not adversely impacted by cloud cover, but DEMs made from sequential satellite passes are incoherent in areas of active lava flows—the very places where topographic

change information is most important. TanDEM-X—the “TerraSAR add-on for Digital Elevation Measurements” mission, operated by the Deutsches Zentrum für Luft- und Raumfahrt e. V. (German Space Agency)—overcomes this challenge. The mission consists of two identical X-band SAR satellites flying in close formation, within a few hundred meters of one another [2]. In bistatic mode, the signal transmitted by one satellite is received by both, and the dual acquisition can be interfered to form a DEM with meter-scale resolution that is coherent everywhere and represents a snapshot of topography [3]. Differencing TanDEM-X DEMs that were acquired at different times over the lava flow field at Kīlauea Volcano therefore highlights changes in topography due to lava emplacement and, when combined with measurements of flow area, can be used to determine volume change over time.

Figure 1. Histogram showing distribution of elevations in areas of no topographic change between the times of the acquisition of the 2005 IFSAR DEM and a TanDEM-X DEM from June 30, 2011. The difference in pixel-value distribution for bare lava (black line) and forested (gray line) surfaces reflects the different scattering properties of rock versus trees. Note that the histograms are not centered on 0, indicating a static offset in pixel values that must be corrected before the June 30, 2011 TanDEM-X data can be compared with other TanDEM-X DEMs.

Figure 2. Volume change due to lava effusion from the base of Pu'u 'Ō'ō cone during August 3–15, 2011. (A) Thickness map derived from TanDEM-X DEM difference map. (B) Volume of August 3–15, 2011, Pu'u 'Ō'ō lava effusion calculated from four independent look angles (several of which have multiple acquisitions over which the volume can be calculated). The average value for the volume of the effusion is $11.6 \times 10^6 \text{ m}^3$.

2. PROCEDURE

All processing of TanDEM-X data was accomplished using the GAMMA software [4]. A TanDEM-X acquisition consists of two SAR scenes—one from the TanDEM-X satellite and the other from the nearly identical TerraSAR-X satellite—that are acquired at the same time. The two scenes are combined to form an interferogram that contains only orbital error and topographic information, since there is no temporal separation in image acquisition. Orbital error is minimized by first using the precise satellite orbits provided with the SAR data, and then selecting ground-control points from a 4.5-m DEM acquired in 2005 by an airborne SAR (“IfSAR”) to eliminate any residual orbital phase. The resulting interferogram, which is a good representation of topography, is then smoothed [5] and unwrapped [6].

3. CALCULATING VOLUME CHANGE AND UNCERTAINTY

The phase contribution of the 2005 IfSAR DEM is subtracted from each TanDEM-X DEM, so the elevations of areas where no topographic change occurred between 2005 and the time of TanDEM-X DEM acquisition should be zero. This provides a convenient means of assessing error and uncertainty in the TanDEM-X DEMs. The distribution of pixel values in areas of no topographic change is Gaussian (Figure 1), indicating that the pixel values are independent and random [7]. Across an entire TanDEM-X DEM there may be some correlated error—for example, from incompletely removed orbital artifacts—but such effects are negligible over areas that span a small percentage of the scene, which is the case for individual lava flows. The mean elevation in areas of no topographic change is

generally $\pm 2 \text{ m}$, while the standard deviation varies widely, from $\sim 3 \text{ m}$ on recent lava flows with no vegetation to $\sim 8 \text{ m}$ in heavily vegetated areas (the higher variance in forested areas is probably caused by radar reflections from both trees and the ground, resulting in a greater spread of pixel values in those areas; Figure 1). Before any calculation of elevation difference, and hence volume change, between two TanDEM-X DEMs, the individual DEMs are normalized to account for static offset in pixel values (Figure 1). The mean elevation and standard deviation for a TanDEM-X DEM are determined for pixels in a test area that should have no topographic change but that is adjacent to an area of interest. The mean elevation is then subtracted from the pixels in the area of interest, bringing each TanDEM-X DEM into a common reference frame.

The August 3–15, 2011, lava breakout from the Pu'u 'Ō'ō eruptive vent (active since 1983) on Kīlauea's east rift zone [8] provides an excellent test for assessing the repeatability of volumes calculated from differencing TanDEM-X DEMs. During that time period, a vent at the base of Pu'u 'Ō'ō cone caused lava stored within Pu'u 'Ō'ō crater to drain and spread out across the west flank of the cone. The ~ 2 -week-long effusion was well documented by field observations and was located in an area that is imaged by four independent TanDEM-X look angles (path 24 strip_007; path 24 strip_006; path 32 strip_008; path 32 strip_009). The area of the flow was determined by incoherence in interferograms that span the event [9]. TanDEM-X DEMs from before and after the effusion were differenced, and the elevation changes within the flow area were summed to determine flow volume. DEM difference maps demonstrate that the flow thickness ranges from a few meters on its periphery to over 20 meters near the base of Pu'u 'Ō'ō (Figure 2A). Volume estimates from all four look

Figure 3. Elevation change due to lava effusion during June 2011–June 2013 from the east rift zone of Kīlauea Volcano as determined by TanDEM-X DEM differences.

angles show remarkable agreement, averaging $11.6 \times 10^6 \text{ m}^3$ (Figure 2B). DEM difference maps that do not span the entire period of the effusion indicate a lower volume, as would be expected. This example suggests that the TanDEM-X-derived volume calculations are internally consistent to within a few percent.

4. TIME-AVERAGED LAVA DISCHARGE RATE

By differencing TanDEM-X DEMs that are sequential in time, it is possible to reconstruct the four-dimensional development of Kīlauea’s east rift zone lava flow field during June 2011–June 2013 (the time period over which TanDEM-X data are available) and to estimate the average lava discharge rate over the time periods spanned by the

individual difference images. The thickness map spanning the entire period (Figure 3) shows that lava accumulation over the two-year span exceeded 30 meters at the base of the cliffs above the coastal plain, in the same place that visual observations documented persistent breakouts and the development of a topographic ramp. The range of lava discharge rates was $1.0\text{--}2.5 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ (black bars in Figure 4). Interestingly, the discharge rate during 2012—a time period when nearly all lava flow activity was on land (meaning that the volume changes derived from TanDEM-X DEM difference maps represent the lava effusion rate)—decreased temporarily during the middle of that year, which is consistent with field observations of sluggish lava flow activity and a lull in both summit and east rift zone deformation. The overall average discharge rate of $2.2 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ during 2011–2013 is well below Kīlauea’s average lava output of $3.5\text{--}4.5 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ during 1983–2003 [8]. Given the absence of significant inflation elsewhere on the volcano, which would be a sign of subsurface magma accumulation, the decreased lava effusion rate may indicate a drop in the rate of magma supply to the volcano. The especially low effusion rate during July–August 2012, which corresponded to a period of no deformation along Kīlauea’s summit and east rift zone (red and blue lines in Figure 4), suggests that magma supply can fluctuate not only over years, but also on timescales of weeks to months.

The configuration and activity of Kīlauea’s eruptive vent during 2011–2013 was such that traditional measures of lava effusion rate, including lava tube studies and tracking of gas emissions, could not be employed. The TanDEM-X DEM difference maps therefore represent the only reliable means of assessing the volumes of lava erupted onto land during that time period.

Figure 4. Time-averaged discharge rate of lava from Kīlauea’s east rift zone eruptive vent determined from TanDEM-X DEM difference maps. Black bars show average discharge rate spanning TanDEM-X DEM acquisitions; bar thickness exceeds formal uncertainty in volume calculation. Gray areas denote periods when lava entered the ocean (i.e., not all lava erupted on land during these periods). Red and blue lines give vertical deformation at the summit and Pu’u ‘Ō’ō (on the volcano’s east rift zone), respectively. Note lull in deformation during July–August 2012, at the same time as a marked drop in lava discharge rate.

5. REFERENCES

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